

An investigation into factors that shape Francophone African EFL learners' beliefs in learning English

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This study investigates the factors that shape learners' beliefs in learning English in sub-Saharan Francophone Africa, particularly the factors that help as well as those that do not help them learn English. The aim is to raise English teachers' awareness of those beliefs so that they can tailor their teaching practices to reflect their learners' uniqueness. Therefore, I used learner reflective journals and focus group interviews to collect data from EFL students at university ($N = 20$; four females and 16 males aged 24 to 42). The findings indicated that (a) teachers' classroom practices, (b) opportunities to interact with other people to develop or test new knowledge, (c) learners' personal effort investment, and (d) the Francophone environment were the factors that affected these learners' beliefs while learning English in Francophone Africa. Among these factors, limited opportunities for interactive speaking activities and Francophone environment did not encourage them to actively engage in English learning.

Keywords: EFL Students; Francophone Environment; Interactive Speaking; Learners' Beliefs; Personal Effort

1. Introduction

Studies on language learner's beliefs have explored learner beliefs using different theoretical frameworks and standpoints to improve second language acquisition (SLA) researchers' and practitioners' knowledge of their learners' beliefs (e.g., Amuzie & Winke, 2009; Barcelos, 1995; Bernat & Gvozdenko, 2005; De Costa, 2011; Fujiwara, 2011; Horwitz, 1999; Li, 2014; Loewen et al., 2009; Mercer, 2011; Metz, 2018; Negueruela-Azarola, 2011; Özdemir, 2013; Wan et al., 2011; Zhu & Wang, 2019). Toward this end, Amuzie and Winke conducted a study that shed light on the variability and dynamism of language learners' beliefs. Their work was grounded in the normative theory framework. A study by De Costa (2011), on the other hand, pointed out the effects that social and ideological tendencies have on language learners' beliefs by applying the contextual and discursive theoretical frameworks. Negueruela-Azarola (2011) and Wan et al. (2011) framed their studies within the sociocultural theory perspective. They aimed to demonstrate that language learner beliefs are developed during social interactions with other people who

facilitate the negotiations and elaboration of new knowledge for them. In addition to their various approaches and standpoints, the studies cited above were conducted in America (Amuzie & Winke, 2009; Barcelos, 1995; Loewen et al., 2009; Metz, 2018; Negueruela-Azarola, 2011), Asia (De Costa, 2011; Fujiwara, 2011; Zhu & Wang, 2019), and Europe (Mercer, 2011; Özdemir, 2013). In fact, the participants of these studies came from America, Asia, and Europe or had learned their L2 in these educational contexts. As a result, their beliefs are mediated by these learning and teaching contexts, the persons with whom they negotiate such as teachers, classmates, community members, and other significant factors such as cultures, technology, economic and political issues.

Because of the contextual factors that affect English learners' beliefs, I do believe that it is not prudent to use the findings of the studies conducted in Asia, America, and Europe with participants from these teaching and learning contexts to predetermine African learners' beliefs in learning English or to plan pedagogical interventions in an African context. A study with African learners and researchers is therefore necessary to better explore learners' beliefs in learning English in the African context. It is hypothesized that such a study can help English teachers from Africa become aware of their learners' beliefs, and also motivate them to take 'actions' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a) that intend to facilitate English learning in their educational setting. As such, the present study used the 'sociocultural theory' initiated by Vygotsky (1978) to investigate the factors that shape the beliefs of learners from sub-Saharan Francophone Africa in learning English in this environment. Based on this theory, an L2 is learned through interaction with other people—students, community members, teachers, etc. In this theory, I particularly focused on the concept of the 'zone of proximal development' (ZPD), explaining that language learners acquire new knowledge during their interactions with others who help them to access new knowledge that is beyond their control through negotiations (Lantolf, 2005). This belief is held by the participants of this study. Grounded in the view that a language is learned through interaction with other people (i.e., through 'socialization'—cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021, 2024), the present study aims to explore the sub-Saharan Francophone students' beliefs regarding the factors that facilitate English learning for them as well as those that do not contribute to successful English learning. The present study tries to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the factors that shape Francophone EFL learners' beliefs in learning English in Africa?
2. Of those factors, which ones help them, and which ones do not help them learn English?

To answer these questions, I conducted the current study with 20 French-speaking learners from Mali.

2. Background

Learner beliefs are a construct that is associated with the learners' behaviors, attitudes, learning experiences, expectations, social and cultural contexts, and ideologies (De Costa, 2011; Sakui & Gaies, 1999). According to Loewen et al. (2009), learner beliefs are a significant individual difference when learning or teaching an L2, which means that they can be used to predict what learners want to learn and also what they expect their teachers to do to help them learn in a friendly and safe environment. While the multiplicity of theoretical frameworks and approaches in the research of L2 learner beliefs (e.g., metacognitive psychological approach, normative theory, contextual and sociocultural theory, etc.) have increased researchers' and teachers' understanding of the construct, they have also revealed that L2 learner belief is a complex and multifaceted variable that must be scrutinized from different perspectives to give another dimension to the research related to it (Barcelos, 2013; Barcelos & Kalaja, 2011; De Costa, 2011). Authors (e.g., Wenden, 1987) who researched the construct from the metacognitive psychological approach considered language learners' beliefs to be stable. However, it is worth noting that Wenden (1999) later observed the variability and dynamism of language learners' beliefs.

However, the results of a study by Amuzie and Winke (2009) revealed that English learners changed their beliefs about learning this language depending on their level of autonomy and the assistance they received from their teachers; Amuzie and Winke's participants were learning ESL in the USA. The findings of their study support the dynamism and variability of learners' beliefs, as explained earlier. As far as De Costa (2011) is concerned, he continues the research on learner belief by grounding his study in ideology and positioning framework with the goal to explain how political and social factors affect foreign language learning. In this vein, De Costa examines how the language ideology of an ESL student impacted her production in English. These aspects are particularly important for language learning and teaching contexts like that of the present study, where teaching innovations are scarce due to the centralized education system, colonial heritage, political and social issues—which together affect foreign language learners' beliefs positively or negatively.

The current study supports the view that language learners in sub-Saharan Francophone Africa believe that the teaching approaches that expose them to real-life situations through interactions with more proficient speakers while learning a foreign language facilitates learning for them. Those pedagogical

approaches in which the teacher remains the director, or those that fail to integrate real-life situations such as political and social issues, are seen as obstacles to successful L2 learning. The particularity of the context, as explained above, makes it necessary to explore the beliefs of English learners in sub-Saharan Francophone Africa.

In other contexts, such as the USA, designing teaching materials that reflect students' specific needs, including their beliefs, with the ultimate goal to encourage them to actively engage in their learning is considered as regular teaching practice. However, this way of teaching that gives some room to the teacher to innovate their teaching practices and therefore depart from the national curriculum that does not respond to learners' expectations is innovative and transformative in sub-Saharan Francophone Africa.

The reasons for these are numerous. For example, the contents of the English courses are determined by the national curricula and final exams. It is worth noting that these demands (national curriculum and national exams) do not leave sufficient room for innovations. The results of this study whether different from or similar to the previous research studies will make a significant contribution by raising Francophone EFL teachers' awareness of their students' beliefs in learning English in this context. It will also advance teachers' understanding of what they should do to help their students succeed in their learning of English, and then avoid tensions in the classroom. This aspect is supported by the findings of a study by Metz (2018, p. 18) on learners' beliefs about language variations in the United State context: "The more accurately we understand students' knowledge and beliefs, the better equipped we will be to tailor our teaching in ways that respond to students' varied needs." Although the findings will not be generalizable to other contexts that are culturally and economically different from Africa, applied linguists and researchers from other fields must continue the research on learner beliefs to include the voice of researchers and learners from under-represented and under-researched contexts such as sub-Saharan Francophone Africa. The same call was launched by Barcelos (2013) although the author did not list any specific contexts (see also García-Ponce et al., 2018).

3. Method

In this section, I describe the (a) participants and setting, (b) the research design and materials, and (c) the data analysis procedures.

3.1. Participants and setting

I collected data from 20 master's level students (4 females and 16 males), who were all learning EFL as part of their graduate program in English translation at Université des Lettres et des Sciences Humaines de Bamako, a public

university. They were all students from one class. The participants' ages ranged from 24 to 42 with 31.8 being their mean age. I administered a free practice Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL) (ETS, 2021) to the participants. The test was composed of three skills (i.e., listening, reading, and writing). Their proficiency levels were intermediate (high B1) based on the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) for Languages (Council of Europe, 2001).

The ethics committee at Université des Lettres et des Sciences Humaines de Bamako gave the researcher the permission to conduct this study, which is the standard in social sciences, including applied linguistics in this context. The participants also gave their consents to participate in the present study, but they were allowed to put an end to their participation at any time without any penalties. Additionally, anonymity was preserved while I reported the findings. I referred to the participants as S₁ (Student 1) to S₂₀ (Student 20).

In Mali, the Master of Arts in English translation can lead to work as a translator, English language teaching positions, or other professions that need proficiency in English. English is taught as a compulsory foreign language in Mali in addition to French, the official language. Students start learning English in most of the public schools from grade seven. It is obligatory for all university students to learn English for three or four years depending on their specific fields. This includes those students whose majors are not English. Although, Mali is a Francophone country, English is the medium of instruction for all those students who are majoring in English. An academic year is composed of two semesters ranging from 13 to 15 weeks based on the License-Master-Doctorate system that Mali adopted a few years ago like most of the Francophone countries in West Africa. Consequently, students study for six semesters to obtain a license degree and four more semesters to complete a master's degree. The master's programs are reserved for high-achieving students evaluated based on their prior academic performance and the scores of the entrance exam.

3.2. Research design and materials

I used learner reflective journals and focus group interviews to design this study and to gain a richer and better understanding of the Francophone EFL learners' beliefs in learning English in Africa from their own perspectives. According to Creswell (2022), these instruments are useful for capturing learners' perceptions about their English learning experiences, but also for better examining the research questions. Additionally, they give each participant a voice by offering them the opportunity to write their critical reflections in their journals and then discuss collectively these comments in small groups during the focus group interviews. Benson and Lor (1999) argued

that questionnaires are not the perfect tools for capturing all the complexities of language learners' beliefs. The findings of a study by Sakui and Gaies (1999) further demonstrated that the items contained in the questionnaires did not allow learners to report their beliefs the way they wished to. Compared with other research methods (e.g., structured questionnaires), reflective journals and focus group interviews help the participants reflect on their learning experiences, including their beliefs collectively and individually and then report on these experiences or beliefs the way they understand them (Allwright & Bailey, 1991; Rose 2019; Winke 2017).

Another reason for selecting focus group interviews and learner reflective journals is explained by the fact that authors of studies within the range of one to 14 participants have chosen qualitative data collection instruments to scrutinize their participants' beliefs about learning a second or foreign language. For example, Barcelos (1995) used observation, interviews, and open-ended questions to collect data from 14 learners. Brown (1996) used recorded videos, stimulated recalls, and follow-up interviews to collect data from seven adult learners. Regarding diary-methods, Ellis (1998) used learner diaries to analyze the data of six adult language learners. De Costa (2011) used interviews, observation, and artifacts to collect data from one participant.

For the present study, each participant made two entries in their reflective journals for a total of 40 entries: one at the beginning of the semester and one at the end of the semester. I instructed them to make an entry about their English learning beliefs by describing the situations that helped them learn English, but also those that did not, and share it with another student who was designated by the classroom teacher (different from the researcher) to read and respond to the entry to make it more interactive (refer to Appendix A for an example of instruction given to the participants).

I also organized a session of focus group interviews with them after the submission of their entries as can be seen in Appendix B that describes the data sources. The focus group interviews completed the journal entries that were written individually. They provided learners with opportunities to discuss their beliefs as a group. Consequently, the focus group interview questions derived from the major patterns found in the journal entries as shown in the following sample questions:

- (1) Could you please describe the factors or situations that really influenced your English learning in Mali and caused you to succeed or fail as a language learner?
- (2) Why do you think that teachers, peers, and family members were the ones who motivated or supported you to achieve higher in your English learning?

3.3. Data analysis

I used thematic analysis (Clarke & Braun, 2017) to identify the features that were used by the participants to describe their beliefs, perspectives, or experiences in learning English as a foreign language in Francophone Africa in their entries and during focus group discussion. According to Clarke and Braun, thematic analysis allows researchers to find major patterns in large data. These patterns are then summarized or classified under categories or themes that can be used to illustrate the various features related to the experiences or phenomenon under investigation.

To achieve this goal, I read several times the data from learners' reflective journals and those from the focus group interviews to have a general understanding of them. After obtaining a general feel of the data, I categorized them according to the factors that shape learners' beliefs in learning English in Africa, specifically the conditions that (a) facilitate as well as those that (b) do not facilitate English learning for them. The themes that were recurrent during the data analysis were classified under these two categories. This way of analyzing data allowed me to find the major features that can be used to explain the participants' beliefs about learning English in a Francophone context.

It is worth noting that a colleague of mine helped me analyze the data to increase the scientific validity, and then reduce the biases. I also shared the report draft with certain participants to ensure that I reliably report the findings and the outcomes of this study on their beliefs in learning English in a Francophone setting the way they narrated them in their journal entries and during focus group interviews.

4. Results and discussion

Overall, the thematic analysis of the data indicated that the English learning beliefs of learners from sub-Saharan Francophone Africa are influenced by (1) the pedagogical approaches used by their teachers, (2) interactive speaking opportunities, (3) learners' personal effort investment, (4) most significant others' roles, and (5) the Francophone environment. I reported the findings based on the themes that were developed from the thematic analysis. I also displayed one or two quotes from the participants to illustrate each theme although the entire data were used to select a theme.

4.1. Beliefs about factors facilitating English learning

- Theme 1: Interactive Speaking Activities Related to Political and National Issues

Barcelos (2013) suggested that teacher educators could integrate language learners' and teachers' beliefs exploration in their programs to prepare pre-

service teachers to examine their own beliefs to better understand those of their future students. As a result, they will be well-equipped to plan pedagogical interventions that respond to learners' complexities and the social changes leading to fluctuations in their beliefs during the processes of teaching and learning a new language.

I observed this aspect in the participants of the present study who did not believe in decontextualized teaching activities and rote learning as successful teaching and learning practices. The mismatch is explained by the fact that the teachers were not aware of their learners' beliefs influenced by their strong desire to develop or test their knowledge through oral interactions and real-life situation problem solving. For example, the participants were attracted by the courses of the few teachers who could respond to their students' desire to interact orally in English. Thus, they held a positive belief about an oral presentation project on democracy. This topic reflected the political situation in learners' country and gave them the opportunity to communicate in English as an interactive, student-centered course that facilitated English learning for them. In other words, the English learning activities are related to a situation that is real and significant for learners, as explained by S₁₈:

I become confident and enthusiastic whenever I am able to use my English to present a real problem in front of many people with technology, and also to receive comments from a qualified person. I really like attending courses that give me these occasions even if I must give a lot of effort to these classes. This was the case for our project about democracy in advanced speaking and listening class. I obtained something tangible during this course and I also tested my proficiency in English and that is the most important thing for me because I am persuaded that I can become fluent in English that way.

Additionally, learners could use the technological equipment that was available to them to prepare and present their project; hence, a lot of enthusiasm and engagement to this course. However, most of the teachers in this context do not try to understand their learners' beliefs and then teach accordingly—a finding that is reminiscent of what Salmani Nodoushan (2018b, 2023b) found about Iranian EFL teachers in Iran. They are more concerned with strictly following a curriculum that is outdated, in my opinion, although the reasons for this choice can be explained by the lack of technological resources, teaching materials, professional training, and economic issues. The finding further indicates that African learners of English believe that they can learn English in Africa if their teachers can provide pedagogical innovations that respond to their desire to interact in English with more proficient speakers. In other words, they believe that their teachers must create

conditions for them to become active learners. Their beliefs were not shaped by the behaviors of certain traditional teachers who flaunted their knowledge without giving their students the opportunity to evaluate or develop their own knowledge, as criticized by S₇:

Most English teachers, who are often referred to as "tcheetcher" [teachers] by students, spend most of their time showing off their English language skills to students. In doing so, they mystify the learning of the English language.

This belief differs from that of the traditional Malian students who viewed the teacher as the sole source of knowledge and strove to imitate or reproduce what they said. These factors combined with economic issues may have also motivated the students to believe that they can succeed in their English learning in Francophone Africa if their teachers adapt innovative teaching practices. For example, most of these students come from poor and middle-class families, and there is no guarantee that they will obtain a visa to attend study-abroad programs in inner-circle countries (i.e., Australia, Canada, Great Britain, USA, etc.). In such a situation, they additionally believe that an exceptional effort investment can lead to successful learning in their own context.

- Theme 2: Personal effort investment

While certain researchers distinguish effort investment from motivation, they believe that they are complementary to better understand the complex and transitional world of L2 learners (Darvin, 2020; Darvin & Norton, 2023). In the present study, effort investment is considered as a characteristic of motivated behavior that influences learners' beliefs in learning a new language. It focuses on the attention, time, and efforts or energy that learners devote to their learning to achieve their significant goals such as becoming proficient in a foreign language (Dewaele & Li, 2021; Hiver et al., 2021; Koné, 2022).

While Amuzie and Winke's (2009) ESL students' beliefs were shaped by their autonomy and the help they received from their teachers, the participants for this study believed that their own personal effort investment is one of most significant factors that guided their path toward success. It helped them stay on track until they achieved their desired learning goal—that is, becoming proficient in English—as illustrated in the following sample comment:

The desire of specialization in English language along with personal commitment have been essential for achieving my English learning goal with success. (S₃)

Another factor that facilitated learning for these students was their capacity to guide their efforts toward the teaching practices that were congruent with their learning beliefs, as described by S₂₀:

I think that only my will and efforts guide my English learning journey, so even bad teaching behaviors did not discourage me. I was just interested in the positive aspects that I wanted to persevere to accomplish my goals and become fluent. (S₂₀)

Additionally, the participants revealed that they continued learning English successfully despite the challenges of not having many opportunities to test their knowledge in real-life situations—or Target Language Use Situations (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020)—with more fluent speakers. For example, they established routines such as attending English clubs and American culture centers, watching English channels, and listening to radios in English to improve their linguistic knowledge (grammar, vocabulary, etc.), their communicative skills (oral interactions, writing, etc.), and also to compensate for the lack of interactive activities, as shown in this student's comment:

I used to listen to BBC and VOA every evening. I also attend English clubs and the American cultural centers. All my roommates were also English students, so we practice English in our room. The most important one was when I worked with a Kenyan who was a pastor. I will go to the church to practice my English with him every two days although I am not a Christian. My only goal was to practice regularly. (S₁₇)

Knowing that the classroom practices alone did not help them succeed in their English learning, the participants invested themselves in their learning by creating conditions that allowed them to access or develop their knowledge by reading English books and listening to English channels. These routines sustained the participants' effort investment, resulting in exposure to the English language, which they thought, helped them achieve proficiency in English:

The learning of the language cannot be limited in the classroom. Outside the classroom, in order to learn, I have to be committed. I have to read books, listen news on English channels and so on. So, the personal commitment has been very important to achieve my goal in speaking English, in addition to my desire to be a speaker of English. (S₂₀)

- Theme 3: The most significant others' roles

The participants' beliefs in learning English were also influenced by other people different from their teachers. They explained that having other persons

(e.g., parents, community members, and any other experts) outside the classroom whom they could negotiate with to have access to new knowledge or to test what they had already acquired in classroom facilitated English learning for them as revealed by S₁₆:

My model who is also my uncle could spend two hours explaining new notions or reading my essays in English to give me some feedback so that I could progress.

Negotiating with other people who could help the participants achieve their learning goals facilitates learning for them and then compensates for the absence of a community of practice. This finding shows that learners implicitly connect their beliefs with SLA theories (i.e., sociocultural theory) although they are not knowledgeable about these theories. This result is also a call for the African EFL teachers to include their learners' learning goals in their teaching practices and depart from the colonial teaching methods, old curricula, and outdated teaching materials that are no longer attractive to their students.

However, the participants for the current study did not explain in their entries or during focus group interviews that English language variations (e.g., American or British English versus local varieties) were factors that facilitated or hindered successful learning for them. This is different from the cases of the participants in studies by De Costa (2011) and Metz (2018). For example, De Costa's participant's positioning was influenced by the variety of English used in the interactions with her classmates. Her belief was shaped by her ability to produce academic English with her peers. Regarding the beliefs of the participants in Metz' study, they were influenced by the race, English variations, and how race is used to determine the variety used by the students. Although the participants of the current study considered interactions with more proficient speakers of English as a factor that helped them learn, they did not see the English as a second language (ESL) context or study-abroad programs as the only options that can be used to achieve proficiency in English. This is contrary to Li's (2014) findings on Chinese students who viewed the ESL environment as an advantage for successful English learning. As a result, these Chinese students adopted a positive belief and higher self-esteem, which in turn positively influences their English learning outcomes.

Although I did not specifically situate the present study in the language ideology frameworks, learners' beliefs were affected by the recent rise of nationalism in certain countries of sub-Saharan Africa (i.e., Burkina Faso, Mali, and Niger), as revealed in this comment:

They [teachers] just give us old books to read and these books do not have anything to do with us and our problems. A good teacher must bring

all sorts of actualities even politic in the classroom to make us react and speak much about something interesting and real. Some teachers do that but most of our teachers just copy from old books (S₁₉).

Therefore, the participants believe that their teachers should develop their own ways or pedagogies of teaching English in their context to facilitate interactions for them rather than blindly adopting techniques that do not align with their English learning beliefs. These participants are more demanding than the traditional African students. They are obsessed by the idea stating that a language is a social tool that should function in a society with other people to survive (Ahearn, 2012). They wanted their classroom practices to reflect these ideologies as written by (S₁₅) in one of her entries:

Some teachers are not even enthusiastic of their job and they just accomplish their roles and they do not care of what we think or want to achieve with English

This finding is a response to the call launched by Canagarajah (2005; 2012; 2023) and Lockett and Shay (2020) to decolonize the English language teaching and learning so that it can meet the expectations set by learners when they decided to learn English.

4.2. Beliefs about factors not facilitating English learning

- Theme 4: Teaching methods not in line with learners' English learning beliefs

The participants believed that the teaching methods such as the assessment techniques (decontextualized multiple-choice questions) used by most of their teachers did not facilitate learning for them:

The compositions [mid-term exams] and the final exams in English are only in written form whereas oral is as important as writing to master a language. This does not motivate students to speak English as they aren't evaluated orally. As a result, students just focus on how to get mark [grade] than learning how to speak English. Some of the English teachers even spend much time speaking French. (S₃)

The students did not only want to learn English in an environment that facilitates negotiations, but they also wanted their assessment practices to be interactive to match their English learning beliefs.

Another hindering factor was related to the teachers who remained the director of their courses without involving learners in the activities, as commented by S₁₂:

The teacher does his lesson. He does everything. Pupils are only following . . . How can someone learn English like that?

These participants believed that learning English could become easier for them if their teachers were able to create conditions for them to use their English with real interlocutors or give them activities that aim to apply what they had learned during the course in real world situations. Hence, the belief that teacher-centered methods hindered learning for them—as revealed by S₆ during the focus group interview:

It was all about memorizing dialogues, sometimes without even knowing the meaning. Also learning some words, grammar rules and doing some reading. Most of the time the teachers do not teach with enthusiasm. They assume the students wouldn't be interested anyway. Many of my friends and I managed to pass the subject without understanding. My first exposure to the English language left me uninterested... Most of the time, students have in mind that the English language is difficult and that, they will never be able to understand it (S₆).

These mismatches between teachers' teaching methods and learners' English learning beliefs caused them to think that only their own effort investment in their learning helped them learn English in Francophone Africa. However, most of their teachers just strictly follow the contents of a program that does not take into account learners' particularities. Thus, there is a need for adapting 'postmethod' approaches (Kumaravadivelu, 2003) such as critical pedagogy, defined as a way of teaching to establish social justice, equity, and inclusion (Canagarajah, 2005; cf. Chaka, 2024; Mapuya, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024).

The aim is to integrate the learners' particularities and needs in the processes of teaching and learning English to satisfy them. This finding also reveals a contrast between what has been perceived as Malian English learners' preferences (memorization, imitation, rote learning, grammar, vocabulary learning, etc.) and how they currently think of their learning to be conceived. Although some of these items (e.g., grammar, vocabulary) received a high score based on the findings of certain studies—e.g., Fujiwara's (2011) study on Thai EFL learners' beliefs, that used BALLI to examine their participants' beliefs—the participants of the present study did not emphasize these items in their journal entries or during focus group discussions as their preferred learning methods. However, this does not mean that they were not aware of the

importance of a rich repertoire of vocabulary during communication. Again, they saw the negotiations as genuine ways to acquire vocabulary and also their usage:

I became more motivated in reading books, such as novels and grammar books and watching videos and listening to songs in English every day for 1 hour to improve my communicative skills. (S₂)

- Theme 5: The Francophone environment

While the participants believed that their personal effort investment and opportunities to interact in the target language facilitated learning for them, they viewed the Francophone setting as a major barrier to successful learning, particularly if the teachers cannot create conditions for oral interactions and negotiations to compensate for this lack. Contrary to the participants from studies conducted in Asia (e.g., Li, 2014) where learners have access to immersion programs (i.e., proficient speakers of English), learners from sub-Saharan Francophone Africa relied on their own personal means to create virtual communities with whom they can interact. It is necessary to reveal that the limited technological resources (i.e., virtual libraries, laboratories, and limited access to high-speed internet) made learning stressful as explained by S₃:

The environment [Francophone setting] remains a handicap for me to reach my objective in terms of learning English. For instance, in my village where people don't speak English, how can I use my English? (S₃)

The finding suggests that the participants view oral interaction and the development of new knowledge through negotiations with other people as the 'sine-qua-non' of successful language learning. These beliefs are also supported by the participants' traditions, social values, and ideologies. These traditions favor group work, collaboration, and interactions with others. It is worth mentioning that these obstacles made learning difficult for the participants, but they did not believe that they prevented them from learning English in a Francophone setting because of their own personal investment in their learning. However, they wished that their teachers could facilitate learning for them by creating an environment that sustains the development of the English language.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the current study framed within the sociocultural theory suggested that African EFL learners' beliefs are shaped by their teachers' ability to tailor their teaching practices to satisfy their students' need of oral

interactions and new knowledge development through negotiations with other people and their own efforts to create conditions for them to negotiate with more proficient speakers. It is noteworthy that the Francophone environment and limited teaching innovations did not prevent students from succeeding in their English learning, although they sometimes decreased their passion for learning English in a Francophone setting. To mitigate the negative influence of the Francophone context, learners created their own virtual communities of practice (e.g., English clubs and online discussion groups) to develop their language skills.

These findings are a call for Francophone EFL teachers, curriculum designers, and teacher educator program leaders to adapt their teaching materials and techniques to their learners' needs. For example, the virtual community created by the participants of this study to interact orally in English can be used by EFL teachers to strengthen learners' personal effort investment and therefore provide them with opportunities to test their English language skills in real-life situations with real audiences. Additionally, teachers can provide learners with opportunities (surveys, checklists, etc.) to explain their learning goals and include them in the syllabus. These innovations do not demand huge financial means because teachers and learners can bring their own created materials that can be used as support for the course. The findings also imply that African learners of English should not be perceived as passive learners who see the teacher as the sole proprietor of knowledge. They believed that the teaching materials should be contextualized by reflecting the current national issues. Their beliefs were finally affected by their strong desire to depart from the colonial school that does not leave any room for innovation and 'creativity' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018a) and to keep with the teaching practices that value their English learning beliefs.

All in all, the present study endorses the idea that EFL learners' beliefs are influenced by their teachers' ability to create genuine conditions for them to develop or access new knowledge that is out of their reach through social interactions and negotiations with other people. Students think that the teaching methods, the teachers' capacity to create situations for them to test or develop their new knowledge with more proficient speakers, and the use of other learning approaches facilitate learning for them. Knowing these factors will raise English teachers' awareness of them, which will eventually help them address their learners' contextual needs and particularities.

Although the study has made a significant contribution to the research on EFL learners' beliefs in underrepresented contexts, it has some limitations related to the participants' social desirability bias. It is noteworthy that I tried to minimize this bias by organizing focus group interviews. Future studies can use multiple-case design associated with social justice and ideology frameworks to

examine learners' and teachers' beliefs in sub-Saharan Francophone context dominated by the ideologies of nationalism and total rupture with the former colonizer (i.e., France). The aim is to facilitate English learning for Francophone African learners of English and other EFL contexts with similar characteristics.

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Appendix: Sample Writing Instruction for Journal Entry two

Hello everybody,

I hope you are doing great.

As we are at the end of this semester, could you please make an entry about the situations or factors that positively or negatively affect your beliefs in learning English in a Francophone context. For example, which aspects of the courses help or hinder your learning of English. Why do you believe that these aspects help or do not help you learn English in Mali? Feel free to add any other information that can be used to better describe the factors that influence your beliefs in learning English in Mali.

Appendix B

Data Sources

Data collection tools	Periods of collection	Data
Learner reflective journals	First entries (20 in total) at the beginning of the semester: Two weeks after the courses started. Second entries (20 in total) at the end of the semester, that is, 10 weeks after the submission of the first entries.	Raw data from learners' written reflective entries.
Focus group interviews	Two weeks after the submission of the second entries. Four focus group interviews in total. Each group was composed of eight persons: one moderator (the researcher who asks questions) one note-taker, one group lead, and five participants.	Field notes from the focus group interviews.